

to 3.90 meq/100 g soil. These are adequate amounts for successful rice production.

Available S was between 7.80 and 30.14 ppm. Soils of Ghumi₂ and Kalihati of Tangail District and Kalmeshwar of Dhaka District were S deficient. Available Zn (2.18-6.20 ppm) is adequate for rice culture.

N content of the leaf blades ranged from 1.32 to 3.07% and P from 0.008 to 0.140% (Table 2). Almost all plants showed N and P deficiency. K content of the plant tissue ranged from 0.39 to 1.79%. Only plants from Majpara had K deficiency. Ca content of leaves ranged from 0.20 to 0.44%. The Ca content of leaves collected from Ghumi₁, Kalihati₂, and Sathalia was low. Mg varied between 0.10 and 0.17%, and all leaf samples showed deficiency. Leaf samples from Tangail and Kalemshwar were S deficient (Table 2). Zn concentration ranged from 12.3 to 58.7 ppm, averaging 29.6 ppm.

Data on soil and plant nutrients indicated that all the soils had N and P deficiency. With few exceptions, soils contained adequate K. Soil analysis indi-

Table 2. Nutrient composition of rice leaf at panicle initiation stage.

Place	Dry matter yield in g (50 leaves)	Nutrient elements in leaf blades						
		N (%)	P (%)	K (%)	Ca (%)	Mg (%)	S (%)	Zn (ppm)
Ghumi ₁	5.0524	1.78	0.014	1.56	0.28	0.14	0.04	32.70
Ghumi ₂	6.3795	1.96	0.034	1.29	0.21	0.12	0.04	45.30
Kalihati ₁	4.1650	1.54	0.014	1.64	0.24	0.12	0.05	40.00
Kalihati ₂	5.7970	3.07	0.048	1.36	0.29	0.14	0.04	41.40
Sathalia	7.1834	2.05	0.018	1.48	0.22	0.10	0.05	31.30
Kalmeshwar	5.2680	1.72	0.027	1.01	0.20	0.12	0.03	33.00
Majpara ₁	3.9700	3.06	0.008	1.48	0.38	0.15	0.11	55.70
Majpara ₂	5.9030	2.31	0.014	0.39	0.30	0.15	0.13	27.70
Rarikhal ₁	4.2365	2.60	0.014	1.68	0.32	0.14	0.10	58.70
Rarikhal ₂	5.1780	2.65	0.009	1.72	0.34	0.15	0.12	42.00
Matlagram ₁	6.4060	1.96	0.018	1.01	0.35	0.15	0.11	45.40
Matlagram ₂	5.2665	2.81	0.008	1.60	0.35	0.14	0.14	45.00
Juair	5.4730	1.74	0.018	1.21	0.38	0.14	0.14	21.00
Bhakindapur	4.2470	1.72	0.014	1.21	0.41	0.15	0.10	15.30
Alipur	4.4180	1.79	0.019	1.20	0.38	0.16	0.12	17.30
Bhakindagram ₁	4.3230	1.72	0.010	1.24	0.44	0.15	0.13	27.70
Bhakindagram ₂	3.2370	1.73	0.008	0.94	0.42	0.16	0.14	24.00
Amjupi	4.3355	1.32	0.018	1.44	0.44	0.17	0.13	21.00
Rajnagar	3.6720	1.62	0.014	1.79	0.40	0.16	0.11	24.00
Tetulia	2.2795	2.22	0.012	1.48	0.38	0.16	0.14	12.30
Ulashi	5.7065	1.24	0.010	1.01	0.40	0.13	0.11	21.00
Pathila	5.3240	2.31	0.017	1.21	0.41	0.15	0.18	18.70
Dattanagar	3.4950	1.45	0.014	1.13	0.35	0.15	0.18	16.30

cated there was an adequate supply of available Ca and Mg in all the areas, but plant analysis showed crops in Ghumi₁, Ghumi₂, Kalihati₁, Kalihati₂, and Satha-

lia to be Ca deficient. Plant analysis showed Zn deficiency in all the areas though soil analysis indicated adequate Zn supply. □

Nitrogen management in rainfed lowland transplanted rice grown on calcareous soil

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The effect of applying different nitrogen sources was studied at the RAU Research Farm during 1981 kharif. Nitrogen sources were prilled urea, lac-coated urea (LCU), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and urea supergranules (USG). A no-nitrogen control and 29, 58, and 87 kg N/ha were applied in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Soil in the field was a calcareous silt loam with 0.76% organic carbon, 8.8 kg available P/ha, 0.12 meq/100 g exchangeable K, and pH 7.9.

Thirty-five-day-old Pankaj seedlings were transplanted at 15- × 20-cm spacing on 23 Jul 1981. Prilled urea was applied either basally or in 3 equal splits at transplanting, tillering, and panicle initiation.

Rough rice yield as influenced by sources and levels of nitrogen.

Source of N	Grain yield (t/ha)				LSD 5%
	29 (kg N/ha)	58 (kg N/ha)	87 (kg N/ha)	Mean	
Prilled urea (basal)	3.3	3.4	3.7	3.4	Source (S) – 0.22
Prilled urea (split)	3.3	3.5	3.9	3.6	N level (N) – 0.17
Lac-coated urea	2.9	3.2	3.6	3.2	S × N – NS
Sulfur-coated urea	3.4	3.7	4.0	3.7	Control vs – 0.14
Urea supergranules	3.4	3.9	4.0	3.7	rest
Mean	3.3	3.5	3.8		
No-N control		2.91			

LCU (34% N) and SCU (36.7% N) having 21% dissolution rate in 7 days were broadcast and incorporated before transplanting. USG were placed 8-10 cm deep between 4 hills immediately after transplanting when the soil began to harden. All plots received a basal dose of 18 kg P and 17 kg K/ha, and a 0.5% ZnSO₄ solution with lime was sprayed on the crop at tillering stage. Drought from heading through harvest reduced yield. After

harvesting a net area of 10.88 m² on 17 Nov grain yield was recorded at 14% moisture.

Averaged over three nitrogen levels, SCU, USG, and split-applied prilled urea produced yields significantly superior to those from basally applied prilled urea and LCU (see table). Grain yield increased significantly with each increase in applied N. Although the interaction between sources and levels of N was not signif-

icant, the data indicated that at 29 and 58 kg N/ha, SCU and USG were more efficient than all other sources. At 87 kg N/ha, SCU, USG, and split-applied prilled urea yielded similarly and more than

basal prilled urea and LCU. LCU was least efficient at all N levels.

Zn deficiency symptoms increased with higher basal SCU and USG N applications. Drought also affected those treat-

ments more adversely.

Results suggest that application of 58 kg N/ha as SCU or USG produces best yields in drought-prone areas with Zn-deficient calcareous soil. □

Nitrogen fertilization and spacing to maximize upland rice yield

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Upland rice is a major crop in eastern Uttar Pradesh, but yields are low because of drought, weeds, poor agronomic practices, and lack of locally adapted improved varieties with good yield potential and high nutrient use efficiency. In 1976 we tested the effect of row spacing and nutrient supply on grain yield of Narendra 1 (IET2232), a semidwarf upland rice.

The crop was grown under natural upland conditions on sandy loam soils at Faizabad at 3 row spacings — 15, 20, and 25 cm — and nitrogen levels — 0, 40, and 80 kg/ha. Fourteen kg P and 25 kg K/ha were applied to all plots. The field was tilled after the first rain in early Jul, and 100 kg seed/ha was direct-seeded in rows. The crop was hand weeded. The experiment was repeated in 1977 and 1978. Weekly rainfall at Faizabad from Jun to Oct 1976 and 1978 is in the table. Total rainfall during the crop season is about 1,000 mm, but is interrupted by drought spells. In 1977 the crop failed because of drought.

Grain yield increased sharply with increased nitrogen, regardless of row spa-

Effect of nitrogen levels and row spacings on upland rice yield, Faizabad, India.

Weekly rainfall distribution during crop season at Faizabad, India

Month	Year	Rainfall (mm)				
		Wk 1	Wk 2	Wk 3	Wk 4	Total
Jun	1976	0	21.6	0	8.6	30.6
	1978	0	55.6	61.2	15.2	132.0
Jul	1976	0	81.8	97.6	32.0	211.4
	1978	2.6	3.4	420.0	75.2	501.2
Aug	1976	109.6	218.0	133.6	77.6	538.8
	1978	13.6	115.2	39.2	12.4	180.4
Sep	1976	0	214.6	13.6	84.6	312.8
	1978	33.2	57.8	41.0	64.0	196.0
Oct	1976	0	20.6	0	0	20.6
	1978	15.2	0	0	0	15.2

Total rainfall = 1113.8 in 1976, 1024.8 in 1978.

cing (see figure). Yield increased from 1.6 t/ha at 0 kg N to 3.6 t/ha at 40 kg N and to 4.1 t/ha at 80 kg N/ha in 1976. Re-

sponse to N was similar in 1978. The 20-cm spacing between rows produced maximum grain yields at 40 and 80 kg N/ha. □

Effect of amendments and presubmergence on Fe and Mn availability in sodic soil and on rice yield

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A field experiment evaluated the effect of adding 12.5 t gypsum/ha, pyrite (equivalent to gypsum on sulfur basis), 30 t farmyard manure/ha, 30 t rice husk/ha at 0 and 30 days submergence prior to transplanting of rice on Fe and Mn availability and rice yield. The experiment

was replicated 4 times in a split-plot design on highly sodic sandy soil with pH 10.6, exchangeable sodium percentage

(ESP) 94, exchangeable Ca + Mg 0.4 meq/100 g soil, organic carbon 0.26%, CaCO₃ 2.75%, CEC 10.0 meq/100 g soil,

Table 1. Effect of duration of pretransplanting submergence and amendments on rice grain yield.

Duration of pre-planting submergence (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)					
	Control	Gypsum	Pyrite	Farmyard manure	Rice husk	Mean
0	0.08	5.19	4.81	3.29	2.70	3.21
30	0.18	5.58	5.43	5.52	4.52	4.24
Mean	0.13	5.38	5.12	4.40	3.61	

CD at P = 0.05, Amendments = 0.23; Submergence = 0.13; Amendments × submergence = 0.29.